

The Role of Talent Management and Human Resource Practices in Organizational Performance

Zueva Oksana

Senior Executive Officer on Professional Administration and Support Westminster
International University of Uzbekistan

Email: ozuyeva@wiut.uz

Abstract

Talent management has become an important strategic element for organizations seeking to improve performance and maintain competitiveness in dynamic business environments. Effective human resource management practices enable organizations to attract, develop, and retain employees whose skills support organizational goals. This paper examines the role of talent management strategies and key HRM practices in supporting organizational development, particularly during periods of expansion. The study focuses on major HR functions such as human resource planning, job analysis and job design, employer branding, employee value proposition, and talent acquisition strategies. The findings suggest that the effective integration of talent management with organizational objectives contributes to stronger employee engagement, improved productivity, and enhanced organizational performance.

Keywords: Talent management; Human resource management; Talent acquisition; Employer branding; Employee value proposition; Human resource planning; Organizational performance

Introduction

In the modern knowledge-based economy, organizations increasingly recognize that human capital plays a critical role in achieving sustainable growth and competitive advantage. Employees' knowledge, skills, and competencies significantly influence organizational performance, innovation, and productivity. Consequently, effective talent management has become a strategic priority for organizations seeking to improve operational efficiency and strengthen their position in the labor market.

Talent management involves systematic processes aimed at attracting, developing, and retaining qualified employees whose competencies support organizational objectives. These processes are supported by key human resource management practices such as workforce planning, job analysis, recruitment, and employee

development. When effectively implemented, such practices help organizations align their workforce capabilities with strategic goals.

This paper examines the role of talent management strategies and HRM practices in supporting organizational growth. Particular attention is given to HR planning, job analysis and design, employer branding, employee value proposition, and talent acquisition strategies. The study highlights how these elements contribute to effective workforce management, especially in organizations experiencing business expansion.

Talent management strategy and HR functions and practices

2.1. What is talent management strategy

In our days of economy and business progress, recruiting and attraction high qualified talent has become a core area of every organization, as employees are one of the crucial components of the organization production, development and progress. According to Baqtayan (2014), talent management “changes the way employees are organized, how they use technology, how their resources are allocated, and how they measure what they do”. Talent management is the guidance of the talent movement within the company and can help an organization to “align the right people with the right jobs at the right time based on business priorities” (Paquet and Rogers, 2008). Talent management is the key component and extremely important for putting the proper worker in the correct position at the required time.

According to Chuai, Preece, Lles (2008) and Baqtayan (2014) the main areas cover by talent management are:

- talent attraction through recruitment and selection;
- retaining essential talents;
- performance management;
- developing talent through learning facilities;
- meeting needs of employees and providing them with work in accordance with their skills and competencies;
- recognizing, compensating and rewarding high performance.

2.2. Importance of talent management strategy

Based on PMI (2013) research it is important to note that the goals of talent development management should be related to organisational strategies and they have direct influence on the company success. According to the Project Management Institute (PMI, 2013), organizations that align talent management with their overall strategic objectives tend to achieve considerably higher levels of project success. In contrast, organizations where talent management is not effectively integrated with organizational strategy experience lower project performance and face a substantially greater risk of financial losses in project investments.

PMI (2013) research also found out that companies that have effectively bring talent management into accordance to company strategy are much more likely to show outstanding results at:

Direction	Description
Meeting common talent challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Engaging people to deliver organizational goals; ▪ Developing high performance teams; ▪ Managing talent through change.
Implementing career paths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Managing performance effectively; ▪ Developing high potential individuals; ▪ Selecting best talent for internal promotions; ▪ Succession planning; ▪ Career progression.
Reducing communication challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Communication across disciplines; ▪ Communication across age cohorts.
Effectively filling open positions and managing contractors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Identifying high potential employees; ▪ Assessing best talent to join the organization; ▪ Finding talent externally; ▪ Success with contractors.

Source: PMI (2013)

2.3. Human Resource functions and practices

According to Porter (1990) and Huselid and Becker (2011) the HR functions and practices are the essence of organizational strategy and competitive advantage, and they should be in line with organisation values and objectives. Primary HR functions

and practices are: recruiting, attraction and selection; training, developing and motivation; employee retention/satisfaction; wage, compensation and benefits.

Different research pointed out that HR practices have positive influence on employees' contribution to increase company performance. Katou and Budhwar (2012) and Dechawatanapaisal (2018) concluded that career development, training, participation and rewards have positive influence on motivation of the employees and they are the main factors that influence staff intention to stay within the organization. According to this research recommendation is provided to organise working culture with attention to the development of employees as well as provide valid compensation. There is a need for organisation to develop HR practice that motivates employees and reinforce involvement behaviour. Regular meetings with line managers should be held in order to implement HR practices in the practice. Further, HR principles and practices should be explained simply to staff members so that practices are clear and do not diverge across departments. These will help employees understand clearly their responsibilities and management expectations.

Based on Appelbaum and Kamal (2000) small and medium-sized enterprises in order to have competitive advantage over bigger companies should pay attention to rising employee satisfaction, which, in turn, minimizes turnover, and lost productivity costs. Other researchers Huselid (1995) and Klass et al. (2002) also concluded with the same result and advices. This finding is directly related and has importance for our organisation, due to our company is a medium-size and we have to work on gaining competitive advantage over bigger companies. Therefore, increasing employee satisfaction should be one of the main aspects which we have to focus on.

To summarise, talent management can be time-consuming and costly for the organisation, however the gain will cover expenses. Guest and Bos-Nehles (2013) recommends to invest in HR practices because HR practices have positive influence on efficiency, productivity, and profitability of the organisation.

Human resource planning, job analysis and design

3.1. HR planning

HR planning topic has been discussed by many researchers. Stainer (1971) identified HR planning as "Human resource planning aims to maintain and improve the ability of the organisation to achieve corporate objectives, through the development of

strategies to enhance the contribution of personnel at all times in the foreseeable future”. Furthermore, Burack (1985) explained it as a process of determining how the organisation should move from the staff location that is present in the organisation to the planned position in the future. According to Lynch (1982) there are two fundamental goals of human resource planning: the effective applying of the present employees; and providing information for the future staff needs in terms of skills, numbers and ages. HR planning works with strategies to get the required amount of employees, with proper skills, to reach company’s objectives and to satisfy the corporate goals. In short, HR planning is the process of effective use of human resources and future employment decisions.

Smith (1976) recommended that in order to avoid redundancy or deficit of certain skill human resource planning process should cover three main steps: demand prediction; supply analysis; covering gap between demand and supply for full apply of proficiency.

According to Idris and Eldridge (1998) for development human resource planning strategy for the organisation next steps should be met:

- *Environmental analysis.* Changes in the technological, economic, legal, and labour market environments should be controlled and examined on HR strategies influence.
- *Review of the internal sources.* It is important to analyse the current staff number, their job-related skills, performance levels (productivity), competences and work approach. This step of analyse will helps to determine HR benefits and drawbacks.
- *Demand forecast.* Forecasting allows to learn about the future employees requirements in accordance with the organisational goals and will help to eliminate the staff shortage.
- *Formulation of human resource objectives and strategies.* Organisation should provide clear vision of HR position and the steps requires to reach this goal.

3.2. Job analysis

According to different research job analysis is the process that helps to analyse duties and skill essential for the position and the nature of person who should cover the spot. Job analysis is preparatory stage for drawing up the job description and specification. Job analysis helps to collect and prepare information for work activities, job context, employees requirements and others.

As Hong and Lin (1995) mentioned in their paper, in order to create model of job analysis we need to:

- know the tasks involved in the job (what needs to be done?);
- know the methods (how is it to be done?);
- identify the required knowledge (what needs to be known in order to do it?).

Methods

There are several methods of job analysis and it is recommended to use *combination* of methods such as questionnaires, observation and interviews.

Observation is a watching by manager the employee performs. This method is limited because not every job's duties can be easily observed; this method is useful for repetitive jobs.

Questionnaire is the widely used method of gathering information because it is easy in use, inexpensive and large number of data could be collected. Questionnaire can cover next topics:

- Knowledge, skills, experience, and qualifications;
- Duties performed daily;
- Duties performed less frequently;
- Equipment and materials used for duties;
- Time spent on different job duties;
- Level of job satisfaction;
- Salary and compensation;
- Work conditions;
- Additional comments (source: blog.careerminds.com).

However, the staff should be able accurately analyse and critically comment on the job information. In this case interview will help to clarify and get more precise data.

3.3. Job design

Job design refers to increasing employees' performance and help to deal with work overload, increase in hours and repetitiveness. According to Strümpfer, (2002) well-designed jobs lead to increased staff well-being, job satisfaction and motivational potential which in turn have positive effect on employee performance and productivity.

This report is recommended to use motivational approach that helps to increase meaningfulness of job through Hackman and Oldham jobs characteristics model. Hackman and Oldham (1976) identified five job characteristics that can predict job satisfaction:

- skill variety (how many skill task/job requires. The more variety of the skill job required the higher is job satisfaction);
- task identity (clear explanation of the task and identifying the successful compliances of the task);
- task significance (meaningful task for individual);
- autonomy (freedom for task compliance);
- feedback (comment on the final result).

Considering this model it is important to pay attention to these five characteristics in order to motivate the employees and increase their productivity. The example could be: task identity refers to what extent the project team has the opportunity to undertake project tasks from beginning to end. Autonomy provides freedom in time frame and decision of how to complete the task. Feedback is the result of the work done.

According to Grant et al., (2010) managers of the organisation have more authority over the job design than over the organization's culture and technological development. Job design has important influence on the productivity and quality of the outcome. According to all reasons above, "job design can be a strategic source of competitive advantage for organizations" (Grant et al., 2010).

Employer branding strategy and employer value proposition

4.1. Employer branding strategy

The employer brand is one of the key factors of company competitiveness in labour market, as attractive companies will recruit talents more easily. Barrow and Mosley (2005) identified the employer brand as "the package of functional, economic, and psychological benefits provided by employment, and identified with the employing company". Martin and Hetrick, (2006) defined employer branding as a positive image in the labour market, while Backhaus and Tikoo, (2004); Berthon et al., (2005) in their research described employer brand as a "high degree of recognition of the organization as employer by a target audience".

The employer brand helps to indicate what it is like to work for the company and what unique value proposition for the employees in the company (Love and Singh, 2011). The brand should meet employees' demand and goals should be relevant and encourage staff (Barrow and Mosley, 2005). The aim of the employer branding is to distinguish the company's characteristics as an employer from its competitors as well as to increase productivity, improve recruitment and retention (Love and Singh, 2011).

According to Kucherov and Zavyalova (2012) cited to The Economist research in 2003 employer brand could be described in the following way:

- promotion of a special image of the company as an employer (60% of respondents);
- part of corporate advertising (28% of respondents);
- appearance and content hiring announcement (7% of respondents);
- other (5% of respondents).

Benefits of employer branding strategy

There are three weighty benefits of employer branding are described in the literature: intensifying recruitment, retention and employee engagement (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004; Edwards, 2010; Love and Singh, 2011). As Barrow and Mosley, (2005) mentioned these improvements can contribute considerably to the overall business performance. Effective employer branding helps to decrease HR costs and improve recruitment performance, create a competitive advantage and familiarize employees with company values (Backhaus and Tikoo, 2004; Barrow and Mosley, 2005; Love and Singh, 2011). According to Berthon et al., (2005) recruitment is the most notable area in which costs can be reduced. Effective employer brand attracts more qualified specialists and well-known company spends less money on recruitment process. Berthon et al., (2005) in his research found out that a company with a strong employer brand for the same positions can offer lower salaries than organizations with weaker employer brands.

Additionally, companies with strong employer brands have higher labour retention thereby reducing employee turnover; have greater personnel satisfaction which is influence on the advertising of the working place; and strong staff engagement provides better performance in total (Berthon et al., 2005; Love and Singh, 2011). Therefore, loyalty of employees positively influences on satisfaction of consumers and financial indicators increase (Barrow and Mosley, 2005).

Van Mossevelde (2010) in his research developed a five-step process for employer branding.

- *First step* is research. Understanding the employer's position in the employment market and defining the applicable action plan (Van Mossevelde, 2010).
- *Second stage* is designing the EVP. "It provides potential and current employees a reason to work for the company and reflects the competitive advantage of the organisation" (Van Mossevelde, 2010). The company should separate itself from other organizations by providing unique proposal.
- *The third phase* is developing of a communication strategy by markets the EVP to target audiences. It is employer responsibility to decide the most effective and efficient channels for reaching the audience (Van Mossevelde, 2010).
- *The last step* is to express the EVP with the right words and images for recognizing the employer in the market.

To sum up, employer brand provides the obvious economic advantage to a company, the salary costs could be saved. Based on the previous research it can be concluded that the advantages of employer branding are greater than the costs. Based on this it is highly recommended to work on developing employer branding for the company and meet employees' needs.

4.2. Employer value proposition (EVP)

Considering the importance and process of developing employer branding strategy it can be seen that designing of the strong EVP is one of the main aspects of the effective employer branding strategy.

According to Noe et al., (2008) and Peterson, (2007) "EVP attempts to sustain a balance between what the employee gives by work performance to the employer and what they get in return". On initial stage of EVP setting company should analyse organization's culture, management style, employees' qualities and employment image. The main purpose of EVP creation is to highlight to the talented people the benefits and uniqueness of the organisation and identify why employee should choose this particular organization. Gering and Conner, (2002) and Bell, (2005) in their researches concluded that "EVP differentiates competitors in the labour market and a powerful tool for gaining employee commitment". Employee value proposition is one of the useful tool in engaging, developing and retaining the labour pool. This point also has confirmation in the literature, according to Chambers et al.

(1998) companies should define the EVP to retain talented employees. Additionally, Kennedy (2013) recommended that EVP should address the rewards, benefits, organisations' policies and practices opportunities, culture and work environment which are the main factors for attracting talents and retaining employees in the organisation.

Creation of the effective EVP is very important for future development of the organisation, leads to increase of performance and competitive advantage by rising employee loyalty and adoption of innovation as well as EVP has positive influence on the recruitment retention process.

Talent acquisition strategy. Recruitment and selection process

The success of each company depends on acquiring the right talents. With the development of the market, talent acquisition becomes more complicated task. "Talent has become the key differentiator for human capital management and for leveraging competitive advantage" (Bhatnagar, 2003). Employees' productivity and commitment increases with the right talent acquisition strategy. Based on Ronn (2007) maximizing team engagement, motivation, and retention is critical in highly competitive environment. Ployhart (2006) pointed out that staffing is a procedure of attracting, selecting, and employee retention to reach organizational goals.

Recruitment and selection process

According to Boxall and Purcell, (2011) recruitment is the most important role of HR, and the success or failure of an organisation depends on the quality of its human resources (Tyson, 2006; Wickramasinghe, 2007). Minchington and Thorne (2007) in their paper remarked that recruitment is about attracting talents effectively and implement advertising jobs using different media. It is beneficial for the organization to attract employees that will make the company productive in its industry.

Recruitment strategies are necessary for making the company an attractive workplace. Therefore, effective recruitment and selection process will provide an organisation with a competitive advantage and reduction of labour turnover. Recruitment process contains position announcing, collecting applicants' responses, preparing and undertaking tests, interviewing and checking applicants for the relevant positions (Armstrong, 2012). These steps are required in order to be certain that qualified candidate is selected for the position. According to Gatewood and Field (2001), recruitment has two aims: to increase the pool of applicants at

minimum cost; and eliminate poor qualified applicants with the help of selection process.

According to Mondy (2010) “Selection is the process of choosing the most appropriate candidate(s) for the vacant position(s) from the job applicants”. Choosing the best suitable member for the vacant position is challenging process for employers (Branine, 2008). Hiring the wrong person can lead to negative consequences such as high training costs, loss of reputation, increased labour turnover, meager production, and a loss of profitability (Chidi, 2013). Overall, the recruitment and selection process starts with the need to complete a vacant position and then carrying out a job analysis to develop the job specifications (Ballantine, 2009).

Based on previous research it is important to develop an organized and effective talent acquisition strategy as far as it affects the profitability and future of the company.

There are two types of recruitment process: Internal and External. External recruitment is the process of hiring people from outside the company (Royal and Althausser, 2003), while internal is recruiting employees for a vacant position by selecting from already existing talents in the organization (Bidwell, 2011). Different researches addressed the importance of these recruitment processes, for example, Bidwell (2011) believes that internal recruitment has more advantages over the external one. However, Baker et al. (1994) argued that external hires tend to have more benefit for the organisation. While, Devaro (2016) holds by an opinion that the choice depends on the characteristics, system and policies of the organisation.

Conclusion

This paper analyzed the role of talent management strategies and human resource management practices in supporting organizational development and performance. The study highlighted the importance of HR planning, job analysis and design, employer branding, employee value proposition development, and talent acquisition processes as key components of an effective talent management framework.

The analysis demonstrates that well-structured HR practices help organizations attract qualified employees, support their professional development, and improve workforce engagement. Moreover, integrating talent management initiatives with organizational strategy allows companies to manage human resources more efficiently and respond to changing business conditions.

Overall, the findings emphasize that investing in talent management is essential for

organizations seeking sustainable growth and long-term competitiveness. By implementing comprehensive HR strategies and effective recruitment and retention practices, organizations can strengthen their human capital and enhance overall organizational performance.

Bibliography

- Appelbaum, H., and Kamal, R. 2000. An analysis of the utilization and effectiveness of non-financial incentives in small business. *The Journal of Management Development* 19, 9/10: 733–763.
- Armstrong, M. (2012), *Armstrong's Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice*, 12th ed., Kogan Page Limited, London, Philadelphia, PA and New Delhi.
- Backhaus, K. and Tikoo, S. (2004), "Conceptualizing and researching employer branding", *Career Development International*, Vol. 9 No. 5, pp. 501-17.
- Baker, G., Gibbs, M. and Holmstrom, B. (1994), "The internal economics of the firm: evidence from personnel data", *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, Vol. 109 No. 4, pp. 881-919.
- Ballantine, I. (2009), "Recruiting and selecting staff in organizations", in Gilmore, S. and Williams, S. (Eds), *Human Resource Management*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, pp. 92-107.
- Baqtayan, S.M.S. (2014). Is Talent Management Important? An Overview of Talent Management and the Way to Optimize Employee Performance. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5 No 23 (2039–2117). Available from <https://doi.org/10.5901/mjss.2014.v5n23p2290>.
- Barrow, S. and Mosley, R. (2005), *The Employer Brand: Bringing the Best of Brand Management to People at Work*, Wiley, Hoboken, NJ.
- Bell, A.N. (2005), "The employee value proposition redefined", *Strategic HR Review*, doi: 10.1108/14754390580000792.
- Berthon, P., Ewing, M. and Hah, L.L. (2005), "Captivating company: dimensions of attractiveness in employer branding", *International Journal of Advertising*, Vol.

24 No. 2, pp. 151-72.

Bhatnagar, J. (2003), “A need for a paradigm shift in HR for knowledge workers”, *Management and Labour Studies*, Vol. 28 No. 3.

Bidwell, M. (2011), “Paying more to get less: the effects of external hiring versus internal mobility”, *Administrative Science Quarterly*, Vol. 56 No. 3, pp. 369-407.

Boxall, P. and Purcell, J. (2011), *Strategy and Human Resource Management*, 3rd ed., Palgrave Macmillan, Basingstoke.

Burack, E.H. (1985), “Linking corporate business and human resource planning: strategic issues and concerns”, *Human Resource Planning*, Vol. 8 No. 3, pp. 133-45.

Chambers, E., Foulon, M., Handfield-Jones, H., Hankin, S. and Michaels, E. (1998), “The war for talent”, *McKinsey Quarterly*, Vol. 3, pp. 44-57.

Chang, W. and Kleiner, B.H. (2002). *How to Conduct Job Analysis Effectively*.

Chidi, O.C. (2013), “Recruitment practices and performance of unionised organisations in the food, beverage and tobacco industry in Lagos State, Nigeria”, *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, Vol. 5 No. 6, pp. 359-384.

Chuai, X., Preece, D., Lles, P. (2008). *Economic Reform and Talent Management in China: A Study of Multinational Companies in Beijing*. 1-15. Retrieved from www.ceauk.org.uk/2008-conference.../Xin Chuai-full-paper.doc

data.worldbank. (2020). Unemployment, total (% of total labor force) (national estimate) - Uzbekistan | Data. [data.worldbank.org](https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SL.UEM.TOTL.NE.ZS?locations=UZ). Available from <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SL.UEM.TOTL.NE.ZS?locations=UZ> [Accessed 10 November 2020].

Dechawatanapaisal, D. (2018). Examining the relationships between HR practices, organizational job embeddedness, job satisfaction, and quit intention. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Business Administration*, 10 (2/3), 130–148. Available from <https://doi.org/10.1108/apjba-11-2017-0114>

Devaro, J. (2016), "Internal hiring or external recruitment", IZA World of Labour, available at: <https://wol.iza.org/articles/internal-hiring-or-external-recruitment/long>

Edwards, M.R. (2010), "An integrative review of employer branding and OB theory", *Personnel Review*, Vol. 39 No. 1, pp. 5-23.

Gatewood, R.D. and Field, H.S. (2001), *Human Resource Selection*, 5th ed., South-Western Publishing, Cincinnati, OH.

Gering, J. and Conner, J. (2002), "A strategic approach to employee retention", *Healthcare Financial Management*, Vol. 56 No. 11.

Grant, A. M., Fried, Y., Parker, S. K., & Frese, M. (2010). Putting job design in context: Introduction to the special issue. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 31(2 3), 145 157. doi:10.1002/job.679

Guest, D.E. and Bos-Nehles, A. (2013), "HRM and performance: the role of effective implementation", in Paauwe, J., Guest, D.E. and Wright, P.W. (Eds), *HRM and Performance: Achievements and Challenges*, Wiley, Chichester, pp. 79-96.

Hackman, J.R. and Oldham, G.R. (1976), "Motivation through the design of work: test of a theory", *Organizational Behavior and Human Performance*, Vol. 16 No. 2, pp. 250-279.

Hong, J.-C. and Lin, Y.-S. (1995). A model of job analysis on industrial occupations. 44 No. 1, (0043–8022).

Huselid, M. 1995. The impact of human resource management practices on turnover, productivity, and corporate financial performance. *Academy of Management Journal* 38, 3: 635.

Huselid, M.A. and Becker, B.E. (2011), "Bridging micro and macro domains: workforce differentiation and strategic human resource management", *Journal of Management*, Vol. 37 No. 2, pp. 421-428.

Idris, A.R. bin and Eldridge, D. (1998). Reconceptualising human resource planning in response to institutional change. *International Journal of Manpower*, 19 No. 5, (0143–7720), 343–357.

Katou, A.A. and Budhwar, P.S. (2012), “The link between HR practices, psychological contract fulfillment, and organizational performance: the case of the Greek service sector”, *Thunderbird International Business Review*, Vol. 54 No. 6, pp. 793-809.

Kennedy, K. (2013), “What’s the difference between the employee value proposition and the employment brand?”, Kenedy Communications Global, available at: <http://www.kennedyglobal.com/about-kennedy-communications-global>.

Kilibarda, P. and Fonda, N. (1997), “Random selection”, *People Management*, December, pp. 36-9.

Klass, B., McClendon, J., and Gainey, T. 2002. Trust and the role of professional employer organizations: managing HR in small and medium enterprises. *Journal of Managerial Issues*, 14, 1: 31–48.

Kucherov, D. and Zavyalova, E. (2012). HRD practices and talent management in the companies with the employer brand. *European Journal of Training and Development*, 36 (1), 86–104. Available from <https://doi.org/10.1108/03090591211192647>.

Lawler, E. (2008). *Talent: Making People Your Competitive Advantage*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.

Love, L.F. and Singh, P. (2011), “Workplace branding: leveraging human resources management practices for competitive advantage through ‘best employer’ surveys”, *Journal of Business and Psychology*, Vol. 26 No. 2, pp. 175-181.

Lynch, J. (1982), *Making Manpower More Effective: A Systematic Approach to Personnel Planning*, Pan, London.

Maheshwari, S. and Vohra, V. (2015). Identifying critical HR practices impacting employee perception and commitment during organizational change. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 28 (5), 872–894. Available from <https://doi.org/10.1108/jocm-03-2014-0066>.

Martin, G. and Hetrick, S. (2006), *Corporate Reputations, Branding and People*

Management, Elsevier, Oxford.

Minchington, B. and Thorne, K. (2007), “Measuring the effectiveness of your employer brand”, *Human Resources Magazine*, Vol. 12 No. 4, pp. 14-16.

Mondy, R.W. (2010), *Human Resource Management*, 11th ed., Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River, NJ.

Noe, R.A., Hollenbeck, J.R., Gerhart, B. and Wright, P.M. (2008), *Human Resource Management: Gaining a Competitive Advantage*, 6th ed., McGraw-Hill Irwin, Boston, MA.

Paquet, S., & Rogers, K. (2008). A talent management framework that will raise your organization’s game to the next level. *Perspective Magazine*.

Peterson, B. (2007), “The employee value proposition: six things you need to know”, available at: www.nettemps.com

Ployhart, R.E. (2006), “Staffing in the 21st century: challenges and strategic opportunities”, *Journal of Management*, Vol. 32, p. 868.

PMI. (2013). *The Competitive Advantage Of Effective Talent Management. Project Management Institute*. Available from <http://www.pmi.org/~media/PDF/Business-Solutions/PMExecutiveSummaryTalentMgmt.ashx> [Accessed November 2020].

Porter, M. 1990. *The competitive advantage of nations*. New York: The Free Press.

Ramesh, A. and Gelfand, M.J. (2010), “Will they stay or will they go?: the role of job embeddedness in predicting turnover in individualistic and collectivistic cultures”, *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 95 No. 5, pp. 807-823.

Ronn, K. (2007), “Rethinking talent acquisition”, *Business Week Online*.

Ross, J. (2011). (PDF) *TALENT MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES: CHINA. ResearchGate*. Available from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/268075569_TALENT_MANAGEMENT_STRATEGIES_CHINA.

Royal, C. and Althaus, R.P. (2003), “The labour markets of knowledge workers:

investment bankers' careers in the wake of corporate restructuring", *Work and Occupation*, Vol. 30 No. 2, pp. 214-233.

Schmidt, F. L., & Hunter, J. E. (1998). The validity and utility of selection methods in personnel psychology: Practical and theoretical implications of 85 years of research findings. *Psychological Bulletin*, 124(2), 262–274.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.124.2.262>

Smith, A.R. (Ed.) (1976), *Manpower Planning in the Civil Service*, HMSO, London.

Stainer, G. (1971), *Manpower Planning*, Heinemann, London.

Strümpfer, D.J.W. (2002), "Psychofortology: review of a new paradigm marching on".

Tian, A.W., Cordery, J. and Gamble, J. (2016), "Staying and performing: how human resource management practices increase job embeddedness and performance", *Personnel Review*, Vol.45 No.5, pp. 947-968.

Tyson, T. (2006), *Essentials of Human Resource Management*, 5th ed., Butterworth-Heinemann, New York, NY.

Unlocking concealed value in the employee value proposition (EVP). (2020). *Human Resource Management International Digest*, 28 (5), 41–43. Available from <https://doi.org/10.1108/hrmid-04-2020-0079>

Van Mossevelde, C. (2010), "Employer branding: five reasons why it matters & five steps to action", available at:
www.employerbrandingtoday.com/uk/2010/03/25/employer-branding-five-reasons-why-it-matters-five-steps-to-action/

Wickramasinghe, V. (2007), "Staffing practices in the private sector in Sri Lanka", *Career Development International*, Vol. 12 No. 2, pp. 108-128.